

MOTIVATIONAL STRATEGIES NEEDED FOR INCREASING STUDENTS' ENROLMENT FOR CAPACITY BUILDING IN TECHNOLOGY EDUCATION IN PUBLIC UNIVERSITIES IN RIVERS STATE

¹Ewe, Ugochukwu C., ²Oluka, Susan N. Ph.D. and ³Njoku, N. Anthony Ph.D.

^{1&2}Department of Technology and Vocational Education, Faculty of Education, Enugu State University of Science and Technology (ESUT), Enugu.

³Department of Industrial Technical Education, Faculty of Vocational and Technical Education, Ignatius Ajuru University of Education, (IAUE), Rumuolumeni, Port Harcourt, Rivers State.

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13936132>

Abstract: The purpose of the study was to determine the motivational strategies for increasing students' enrolment for capacity building in Technology Education in public Universities in Rivers State. Two research questions in line with the purpose of the study were formulated while two null hypotheses were tested at .05 level of significance. The study adopted a survey research design. The population for the study was 100 Technology Education lecturers, comprising 90 male Technology Education lecturers and 10 female Technology Education lecturers from public Universities in Rivers State. There was no sampling as the population was of manageable size. A thirty-eight item statements questionnaire was designed to collect data for the study. Three experts validated the instrument. Cronbach's Alpha reliability coefficient was used to determine the internal consistency of the instrument yielded .92. The data collected for the research questions which guided the study were answered using mean and standard deviation, whereas the null hypotheses of the study were tested using t-test statistics. The results of the study show that the intrinsic motivation and extrinsic motivation related strategies are for increasing the enrolment of students for capacity building in Technology Education in public Universities in Rivers State. It was recommended that government and NGOs should give well packaged bursary awards or scholarships and automatic employment to students of Technology Education as it will attract more students into the programme.

Keywords: Motivation, Strategies, Students' Enrolment, Technology Education, and Capacity Building.

1. INTRODUCTION

University is one of the tertiary institutions that offers degree programmes in Nigeria. The agency in charge of accrediting the programmes is National Universities Commission (NUC). University education according to Federal Republic of Nigeria (2013) is charged with the responsibility of maximum contribution to national

development. Universities in Nigeria could either be private or public. Public University is the university that is owned and managed by the government. The public University is either owned by Federal Government or State Government. The state owned public universities are managed by the state that established it. There are numerous numbers of programmes run in the public Universities and one of such programmes is Technology Education. Technology Education (TE) is the study of technology in which students learn about the processes and knowledge related to technology. As a field of study, it covers the human ability to shape and change the physical world to meet needs by manipulating materials and tools with techniques. It is the training of an individual towards the acquisition of practical and salable skills, abilities and knowledge leading to a particular occupation to live productively in the society. According to Okoye and Arimonu (2016), technology education is the training of technically oriented personnel who are to be the initiators, facilitators, and implementers of technological development of a nation. The authors meant that, this training of its citizens on the need to be technologically literate would eventually lead to self-reliance and sustainability. They believed that technology education, more than any other profession has direct impact on the development of individual in particular and the country in general.

According to Abudulahi (2016) Technology Education is a form of education that is perceived as one of the most crucial elements in enhancing economic productivity. In this new economic environment as observed in most developed countries in the world, TE is expected to produce and supply intermediate craftsmen, technicians, semi-skilled and skilled manpower that will be able to function very well in all sectors of the industry critical to national development, (Okeke 2002 as cited in Okwelle & Agwi, 2018). On the other hand, TE contributes so much in developments ranging from electrical and electronics technology, metal work technology, mechanical technology, automobile technology, building technology, woodwork technology etc. Technology education is practical oriented education which makes it unique in its content and approach thereby demanding special attention (Okoye and Arimonu, 2016). Therefore, Technology Education is designed to offer students the opportunity of improving themselves in their general proficiency, especially in relation to their present or future occupation. Effective teaching in technology education in Universities involves: Hands-on Learning: Practical experiences, simulations, and projects, Interdisciplinary Approaches: Integrating multiple disciplines to foster holistic understanding (Akkerman & Bakker, 2011), Real-World Applications: Connecting theoretical concepts to industry practices, Collaborative Learning: Encouraging teamwork, communication, and problem-solving., Flipped Classroom: Blending lectures with interactive online content (Bishop & Verleger, 2013), Project-Based Learning: Student-centered, inquiry-based projects, Assessment and Feedback: Regular evaluation and constructive feedback, Emphasis on Soft Skills: Developing essential skills like communication, teamwork, and time management (ABET, 2017). Incorporating Emerging Technologies: Staying updated with industry trends and innovations. Reflective Practice: Encouraging students to reflect on their learning and experiences. Nuru (2017) opined that changes in any nation's economy is required to prepare young people for the jobs of the future

of which Technology Education has crucial roles to play. Technology education in Nigerian universities is carried out through various methods, including: Teaching Methods: Lectures, Practical sessions (labs, workshops), Project-based learning, Case studies, Group discussions, Field trips, Online learning platforms (e-learning). Some of the Facilities used are: Computer laboratories, Engineering workshops, Libraries with digital resources, Internet connectivity, Virtual reality and simulation labs. This is a general overview, and specific practices may vary across universities. Okwelle and Agwi (2018) noted that since the introduction of Technical and Vocational Education and Training (TVET) in Nigeria education system years ago, enrolment in TVET programme in Nigeria has remained low. This development according to Puyate and Agwi (2017) is more disturbing on female students' participation in TVET programme in Nigeria. Furthermore, Ukachukwu (2015) posited that the low enrolment of students into technology education is a source of worry to all and sundry. In line with this view, Auta, *et al.*, (2023) stated that the total enrolment figure into Technical Education programme in Nigeria 2019/2020 academic year was less than 6%. The authors advocate for concerted efforts by all stakeholders to address the challenges as an opportunity to improve the quality and relevance of technology education. Through this, universities in Nigeria can play a pivotal role in producing a highly skilled technical workforce that can contribute to the economic development and prosperity of the country annually.

Oluka (2023) had identified major factors responsible for low enrolment of students into TE programme to include among others: poor funding by the government, no incentive to TE staff irrespective of the hazards associated to their job in the workshop. Inadequate supply of staff, equipment, tools, and infrastructural facilities scare people away from the technology education programme. Other factors include: gender, ignorance of the objectives of the programme by government and the citizenry. Furthermore, Ogbondah (2021) stated that some challenges of TE programme are paucity of fund, inadequate personnel, inadequate and non-functional facilities, poor perception from the society, and brain- drain syndrome amongst others. The current reform of TE system in Nigeria in the 21st century seems to have not fully addressed the impediments to technology education development in the country. The 21st century is knowledge driven; a technologically oriented era where education programme involves action and skills, and therefore, should need further intensified efforts geared towards repositioning and marketing technology education institutions with a view to making them attractive to prospective students. This could only be possible with the employment of certain motivational strategies among other salient variables, techniques, and practices with total commitments from the citizenry, especially the governments.

Motivation is the inner energetic driver which always propels man to a greater height. Uzoeshi and Iwundu (2014) defined motivation as the innate force which cannot be deterred by psychological forces. It could also be conceived as a drive or push which energizes man into action or towards the accomplishment of a task or tasks. Motivation could be intrinsic or extrinsic in nature. Intrinsic motivation stands for the motives that come from within an individual such as interest, aptitude, intelligence, high esteem, self-confidence, and meaningfulness (Fashoyin, 2014). Motivation means to engage in a behavior because of the inherent satisfaction of the activity

rather than the desire for reward of specific outcome. Intrinsic motivation come solely from oneself that is within an individual and not from external forces like incentive. While extrinsic motivation comes from external of the individual. It is determined by extraneous or environmental factors; namely: parents, peers, the society, the mass media, the church, the school, the culture, and the government (Inyiagu, 2015). Extrinsic motivation is a motivation driven by external rewards. It means that it comes from a positive reinforcement such as a reward, or negative reinforcement such as a punishment. Therefore, both intrinsic and extrinsic motivational approaches are needed motivational strategies to enhance students' enrolment into technology education for capacity building.

Strategies, according to Njoku, *et al.*, (2017) are the various measures that could be employed by teachers/lecturers or any other personnel to improve an existing system to achieve success. It is plan of action designed to achieve an aim. Literature has it that there have been vigorous searches for strategies to increase students' enrolment for capacity building into technology education. Extrinsic motivation and intrinsic motivation related strategies should be investigated, employed in the expectation to achieving huge success in increasing enrolment of students into TE programme. The extrinsic motivation related strategies are those strategies championed by external publics like, – parents, government, non-governmental organization, and the public, while the intrinsic motivation related strategies are those internal variables involving students and staff to make the enrolment of students high. These motivational strategies according to Njoku *et al.* (2017) are the attributes and attitudes of the parents, government, students, and staff amongst others to make enrolment of students into the TE programme high. Zehra (2021) stated that strategies are a framework within which an organization defines possible means of achieving goals and objectives. Thus, strategies help to explore ways, sources, collaborations, opportunities which are intended to yield results in the medium- and long-term specific problems. Hence, several strategies ought to be employed to increase students' enrolment for capacity building in Technology Education. Capacity building is the process by which individuals and organizations obtain, improve, and refrain themselves and their staff to improve their skills and knowledge acquisition in order to do their jobs competently. Njoku (2023) defined capacity building as the process of developing and strengthening the skills, instincts, abilities, processes, and resources that organizations and communities need to survive, adapt, and thrive in a fast-changing world. Capacity building include leadership development and planning for future collaboration, Individual capacity building activities include training and mentorships. Organizational capacity building activities focuses on a broader scale. Oby (2022) maintained that capacity building is synonymous with capacity development which is the improvement in an individual's or organization's facility to produce, perform or display; thereby, encourages an individual and/or organization to enroll into a programme for sustainability.

Enrolment is an act of putting oneself or someone into official list of members of a group, course, or college; it is the act of enrolling into an institution or a course. Improving students' enrolment for capacity building in Technology Education in public Universities in Rivers State is important for the purpose of bringing in enough candidates to be trained to man the nation's industry at the sub-professional levels for national development. In

this context, enrolment connotes the total number of students properly registered and/or attending classes in technology education programme in the public Universities. Enrolment of students into the TE programmes cannot just happen, but must be driven by some forces, and one of such forces is motivational strategies. These are ways to help oneself or others achieve goals and stay motivated. Such ways include the use of incentives; introduction to new challenges; visualization of the process and taken leadership (Mohammed *et al.*, 2023). Therefore, motivational strategies are tactics, techniques, or approaches to encourage students to participate in a process. For TE to have high students' enrolment, McInerney, (2019). Identified motivational strategies for increasing students' enrolment for capacity building into TE programmes in public Universities in Rivers State as mission-driven approach; understanding student preferences; painting clear picture; relationships matter; building a community; goal setting and feedback; choice and relevance among others. A critical look at the motivational strategies shows the process involving both intrinsic publics (students and staff) and extrinsic public (parents, government, and non-governmental organization,), with a common goal of stimulating a better understanding of the roles, objective, accomplishments and needs of the university. In the same view Inyiagu (2015) identified some of the motivational strategies for students' enrolment into TE programme to include: proper knowledge of each occupation, interpretation of the characteristics and opportunities available to the students in TE programme, creating awareness within and outside the school, provision of funds to the school to procure resources for TE programme, among others. To this end, there is therefore, the need to assess how the intrinsic and extrinsic motivation related strategies are being utilized to increase the students' enrolment for capacity building in Technology Education in public Universities in Rivers State.

Statement of the Problem

Irrespective of the emphasis placed on the need for Technology Education programmes by the Federal Government of Nigeria (FRN, 2013), there is still poor students' enrolment into TE programme in the public Universities. The major factors of poor students' enrolment into the Technology Education programme could be attributed to personal attitude, societal perception, and unattractiveness of the programme amongst others. Several studies have been carried out on enrollment trends in recent years. For instance, Mohammed, Ifechukwu & Nnaemeka, (2023), in their study reveals that that the enrolment trends into technical education programmes have witness an intermitted negative fluctuation in the last ten (2013-2023) years revealing that 6% enrollment quota was filled in 2019/2020 academic year. Oviawe, (2017) studied on Students' Enrollment in Technology Education Programmes asserted that technology education has remained detested to a greater extent by many Nigerian parents and even students as detected in the low students' enrollment into technology education programmes. Similarly, in a study conducted by Dokubo and Deebom (2017) on "Gender Disparity towards Students enrollment in Technical Education in Rivers State: Causes, Effects and Strategies". The study revealed amongst others that poverty, preference of male child, cultural and religious beliefs were causes of female folk's low enrolment into technical education programmes in Rivers State. The trend witnessed by several researchers is

disturbing and needs urgent intervention to arrest the danger of lacking trained personnel to man the nation's industries at sub-professional levels for national development. Therefore, this study tends to determine the motivational strategies needed for increasing students' enrolment for capacity building in Technology Education in public Universities in Rivers State.

Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of the study was to determine the motivational strategies needed for increasing students' enrolment for capacity building in Technology education in public Universities in Rivers State. Specifically, the study sought to determine:

1. the intrinsic motivational strategies needed for increasing students' enrolment for capacity building in technology education in public Universities in Rivers State.
2. the extrinsic motivational strategies needed for increasing students' enrolment for capacity building in technology education in public Universities in Rivers State.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. What are the intrinsic motivational strategies needed for increasing students' enrolment for capacity building in technology education in public Universities in Rivers State?
2. What are the extrinsic motivational strategies needed for increasing students' enrolment for capacity building in technology education in public Universities in Rivers State?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were tested at .05 level of significance.

HO₁: There is no significant difference between the mean response scores of male and female lecturers of TE programmes on the intrinsic motivational strategies needed for increasing students' enrolment for capacity building in technology education in public Universities in Rivers State.

HO₂: There is no significant difference between the mean response scores of male and female lecturers of TE programmes on the extrinsic motivational strategies needed for increasing students' enrolment for capacity building in technology education in public Universities in Rivers State.

Research Method

The research design employed in the study was survey research design, aimed at determining the motivational strategies needed for increasing students' enrolment for capacity building in Technology Education in public Universities in Rivers State. Survey research is a quantitative research method that involves collecting data from a sample of participants through self-report measures, typically using questionnaires or interviews (Creswell, 2014). It aims to gather information about attitudes, beliefs, opinions, or behaviors of a population.

The study was conducted in public universities in Rivers State. The population is one hundred (100) Technology Education lecturers which comprised of 10 female TE lecturers and 90 male TE lecturers in the two public

Universities in Rivers State, namely Ignatius Ajuru University of Education, Port Harcourt, and Rivers State University, Port Harcourt. The entire population of one hundred respondents was used for the study. No sampling was done since the population size was manageable.

A 38-item structured questionnaire titled: "Motivational Strategies for Increasing Students' Enrolment for Capacity Building in Technology Education (MSISECBTE) in Public Universities in Rivers State, was the instrument used to collect data for the study. The instrument had two parts - part A and part B. Part A was designed to elicit information on the biodata of the respondents using such information as the status of the respondents. Part B was made up of two sections: section 1 and section 2. Section 1 contained 20 items centered on the intrinsic motivation related strategies needed for increasing students' enrolment for capacity building into TE programme, and section 2 contained 18 items centred on the extrinsic motivation related strategies needed for increasing students' enrolment for capacity building into TE programme. The instrument was face validated by three experts, one from the Department of Technology and Vocational Education; Department of Mathematics and Computer Education (Measurement and Evaluation), Enugu State University of Science and Technology (ESUT), Enugu and the other from the Department of Industrial Technical Education, Ignatius Ajuru University of Education, Rumuolumeni, Port Harcourt. The comments of the validates guided the modifications of the final instrument used in data collection for the study. The reliability of the instrument was obtained using Cronbach Alpha. The coefficient of reliability computed from result of a pilot study conducted with 5 female TE lecturers and 20 male TE lecturers from Niger Delta University Wilberforce, Bayelsa State yielded .92. A total of 100 copies of the instrument were distributed and collected from the respondents directly by the researcher with the help of two research assistants on the spot. The total number of copies retrieved was 100, representing 100% return rate, and the number was used for data analysis of the study.

The instrument has a five-point rating scale with Strongly Agree (SA) = 5 points; Agree (A) = 4 points; Undecided (U) = 3 points; Disagree (D) = 2 points and Strongly Disagree (SD) = 1 point as response categories. The descriptive statistics of mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions. An item with a calculated mean value equal to or greater than 3.00 was agree (A), Where the calculated mean of an item with less than 3.00, such item statement was disagree (D). The null hypotheses were tested using t-test. Where the value of the t-test was equal or greater than table value at .05, the hypothesis is rejected, if otherwise, do not reject.

Results

The results of data analysis of the study are presented in the Tables 1 to 4 accordingly.

Research Question 1: What are the intrinsic motivational strategies needed for increasing students' enrolment for capacity building in Technology Education in public Universities in Rivers State.

Table 1: Mean Scores on the Intrinsic Motivational Strategies for Increasing Students' Enrolment for Capacity Building in TE Programme

S/N	Intrinsic motivational Strategies include:	Male Lecturers N=90	TE	Female Lecturers N=10	TE	Overall N=100	Decision
		\bar{X}	SD	\bar{X}	SD	\bar{X}_G SDG	c.
1.	providing students with the knowledge of the advantages of each occupation in TE programme.	3.69	1.28	4.78	1.12	4.24 1.20	A
2.	providing students with the knowledge of the limitations of each occupation in TE programme.	3.90	1.22	4.43	1.18	4.12 1.20	A
3.	interpreting the opportunities available to the students in TE programme.	3.70	1.18	3.96	1.16	3.83 1.17	A
4.	helping students understand themselves better so that they can develop an understanding of their opportunities in TE programme.	4.70	1.14	3.87	1.21	4.24 1.18	A
5.	assist in rewarding the students in TE programme.	3.51	1.35	3.92	1.18	3.72 1.27	A
6.	establishment of viable young peoples' clubs in all areas of technical and vocational education in the universities.	4.68	1.12	4.12	1.12	4.40 1.12	A
7.	assist in inviting successful entrepreneurs in all areas of	3.62	1.41	4.20	1.14	3.91 1.28	A

	technical and vocational education in school to serve as role models to students.							
8.	give career talks to students	4.12	1.12	3.70	1.18	3.91	1.15	
9.	assist students to develop an acceptable self-image and reliable attitude as necessary precursor to the vocation.	3.57	1.21	3.56	1.25	3.72	1.23	A
10.	assist students to develop and execute career plans which will help them in achieving their career goals.	3.79	1.18	4.05	1.13	4.01	1.16	A
11.	encouraging lecturers to develop themselves for effective TE programmes.	4.20	1.11	4.29	1.15	4.25	1.13	A
12.	recruiting qualified lecturers for teaching effectively in TE programme.	3.96	1.16	4.21	1.18	4.09	1.17	A
13.	in-service training of TE lecturers in order to keep abreast of innovation so that, they in turn transmit the knowledge to the students.	4.78	1.12	3.87	1.35	4.33	1.24	A
14.	training materials to be made available for workshop activities.	3.85	1.18	3.78	1.21	3.82	1.20	A
15.	number of courses be reduced.	3.42	1.41	3.09	1.61	3.26	1.51	A
16.	improving in practical works in school.	4.06	1.25	4.35	1.76	4.21	1.51	A
17.	retaining of high flyers in TE programme after graduation.	3.78	1.21	3.92	1.18	3.85	1.20	A
18.	classroom dynamics and right teaching methods be employed.	4.06	1.25	3.87	1.21	3.97	1.23	A
19.	encouraging good class participation of students.	3.56	1.25	4.78	1.12	4.17	1.19	A
20.	assist in exposing students to field trips in related companies and firms.	4.41	1.11	3.97	1.18	4.19	1.15	A
	Cluster Mean/SD	3.97	1.21	4.04	1.23	4.02	1.22	A

Source: Field Survey, 2024.

The results shown in Table 1 revealed that the respondents declare their level of agreements on the 20 items, as the intrinsic motivational strategies needed for increasing students' enrolment for capacity building in TE programmes in public Universities in Rivers State. The cluster mean for the table was 4.02 and the standard deviation is 1.22. This implies that all the items' statements are criteria for increasing students' enrolment into TE programmes in public Universities in Rivers State.

HO₁: There is no significant difference between the mean responses of male and female lecturers of TE on the intrinsic motivational strategies needed for increasing students' enrolment for capacity building in technology education in public Universities in Rivers State.

Table 2: Summary of t-test Results of Mean Responses of Male and Female Lecturers of TE on the Intrinsic Motivational Strategies for Increasing Students' Enrolment into TE.

Respondents		X	SD	N	Df	t-cal	t-table	Remarks
Male lecturers	TE	3.97	1.21	90	98	.12	1.96	Not
Female lecturers	TE	4.40	1.23	10				Sig.

The results in Table 2 showed that the calculated t-value (.12) is less than the critical value (1.96) at .05 level of significance and 98 degrees of freedom. The null hypothesis was not significant and therefore not rejected. The implication of this result is that both male and female TE lecturers in the public Universities in Rivers State hold the same opinion on the intrinsic motivational strategies for increasing students' enrolment for capacity building in TE in public Universities in Rivers State.

Research Question 2

What are the extrinsic motivational strategies needed for increasing students' enrolment for capacity building in technology education in public universities in Rivers State?

Table 3: Mean Ratings on the Extrinsic Motivational Strategies for Increasing Students' Enrolment for Capacity Building in TE Programme.

S/N	Extrinsic Motivation Strategies include;	Male Lecturers N=90	TE	Female Lecturers N=10	TE	Overall N=100			
		\bar{X}	SD	\bar{X}	SD	\bar{X}_G	SDG	Decision	c.
1.	allowing children and wards to take decisions on their own based on their interest and aptitude.	4.28	1.12	3.50	1.10	3.89	1.11	A	

2.	adequate financial support to students for buying of TE materials in schools.	3.78	1.20	3.61	1.14	3.70	1.17	A
3.	enlightening children on the benefits of participating in counseling activities in schools.	4.05	1.01	3.90	1.11	3.98	1.06	A
4.	parents should act as resource persons to schools as it concerns important TE.	3.50	0.81	3.51	0.92	3.51	0.87	A
5.	parents should regularly consult counselors of TE programmes on the students' performance in school.	3.57	0.79	3.58	0.81	3.58	0.80	A
6.	non-governmental should help in giving scholarship to students.	4.21	1.12	3.71	1.13	3.96	1.13	A
7.	non-governmental organizations should assist in the provision of funds to the school.	5.00	0.00	4.50	0.50	4.75	0.25	A
8.	government should help in giving scholarship to the candidates wishing to find a career in TE.	4.78	1.21	4.50	1.11	4.64	1.16	A
9.	government should ensure that adequate TE programme materials are readily available.	4.30	1.71	4.10	1.21	4.20	1.46	A
10.	there should be regular supervision of TE programme in schools.	4.28	1.12	3.16	1.14	3.95	1.13	A
11.	there should be a change in societal negative attitude towards TE programme.	3.50	0.81	3.57	0.92	3.54	0.87	A
12.	there should be automatic employment for TE graduates.	4.78	1.10	4.60	1.13	4.69	1.12	A
13.	parents should change their negative attitude towards TE programme.	3.87	1.13	3.62	1.11	3.75	1.12	A

14.	there should be awareness creation for TE programme in order to popularize it.	4.79	1.23	4.20	1.13	4.50	1.18	A
15.	career counseling services should be provided for students.	3.82	1.11	3.81	1.14	3.82	1.13	A
16.	TE programme should be given its pride of place in policy formulation.	4.02	1.32	4.01	1.33	4.02	1.33	A
17.	special bursary/allowance to students by TE by government.	4.85	1.12	4.85	1.14	4.85	1.13	A
18.	government should give loan to parents whose children are to enroll into TE programme.	3.95	1.20	3.50	1.20	3.73	1.20	A
Cluster Mean/SD		4.19	1.06	3.93	1.07	4.06	1.07	A

Source: Field Survey, 2024.

The results of Table 3 showed that all the respondents express their level of agreements on the 18 items statements as the extrinsic motivational strategies needed for increasing students' enrolment for capacity building into TE programme in public Universities in Rivers State. The cluster mean for the table was 4.06 and the standard deviation is 1.07. This is an indication that all the items are regarded as extrinsic motivational strategies needed for increasing students' enrolment in public universities in Rivers State. The result of the standard deviation indicated that the respondents were very closed in their responses and hence the disparity in their opinions is slim.

HO₂: There is no significant difference between the mean responses of male and female lecturers of TE on the extrinsic motivational strategies needed for increasing students' enrolment for capacity building in technology education in public Universities in Rivers State.

Table 4: Summary of t-test Analysis of Mean Responses of Male and Female TE Lecturers on the Extrinsic Motivational Strategies for Improving Students' Enrolment into TE.

Respondents		X	SD	N	df	t-cal	t-table	Remarks
Male lecturers	TE	4.19	1.06	90	98	.73	1.96	Not
Female lecturers	TE	3.93	1.07	10				Sig.

The results in Table 4 show that the calculated t-value (.73) is less than the critical value (1.96) at the .05 level of significance and at 98 degrees of freedom. The result of the analysis was not significant and was therefore not rejected. This implies that there is no significant difference between the opinion of male and female TE lecturers on the extrinsic motivational strategies needed for increasing students' enrolment for capacity building into technology education in public Universities in Rivers State.

Discussion of Findings

The findings of the study in table 1 revealed that the respondents agreed that the items are regarded as intrinsic motivational strategies for increasing students' enrolment for capacity building in TE in public Universities in Rivers State. The findings agree with the position of Fashoyin (2014) who noted that technology education (TE) will have high enrolment rate if students are presented with successful entrepreneurs in all areas of technical and vocational education in school to serve as role models to them. The study showed that there is no significant difference between the mean response scores of the male and female TE lecturers with respect to the intrinsic motivational strategies for increasing students' enrolment for capacity building into technology education in public University in Rivers State. This is consistent with Okwelle and Agwi (2018), who posited that participating in activities that will correct the poor image of TVET programmes to the public will create room for enrolment of female students into TVET programme.

Results in table 3 depict the extrinsic motivational strategies for increasing students' enrolment for capacity building into TE programme. The results show that the itemized are the extrinsic motivational strategies needed for students' enrolment. Some of the identified extrinsic motivational strategies are adequate financial support to students for buying TE materials in schools, giving of scholarship to the candidates wishing to take a career in TE, giving of special bursary to students of TE by State/Federal government, amongst others. This agrees with the findings of Puyate and Agwi (2017) that for the objective of improving female students' enrolment and overall increase in students' enrolment in TE programmes, that appropriate sustainable strategies must be taken which must involve education policy makers, administrators, teacher, school heads, parents and co-operate bodies. Further, the study revealed that there is no significant difference between the opinions of male and female TE lecturers with respect to the extrinsic motivational strategies needed for increasing students' enrolment into TE programme. This agrees with Inyiagu (2015) who stated that external publics like education policy makers, government, school administrators, parents are the key players in students' enrolment into TE programme in Nigeria. With this backdrop, all and sundry are called to and should be involved in increasing the enrolment of students in TE programmes with the enthusiasm to achieve and ripe the laudable objectives of the programme.

Conclusion

Public Universities in Nigeria offering technology education programmes need some motivational strategies and personnel to communicate the vision, goals, missions, accomplishments, and challenges to the public. This is crucial to correct the poor societal perception of TE programmes in Nigeria in order to have students enrolled in the programme. The researcher vehemently believes that the intrinsic and extrinsic motivational strategies are positive forces for the enrolment of students into TE programme in Nigeria's public Universities and Rivers State in particular.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made:

1. Rewarding outstanding students' achievement through awards, scholarships and automatic employment should be given urgent attention by TE institutions stakeholders.
2. Government at all levels should give well packaged bursary awards, organize awareness programmes in the society and scholarship awards to students of TE. This would attract other students into TE programmes.

References

ABET (2017). Criteria for Accrediting Engineering Programs.

Abudulahi, E. N. (2016). Technical Vocational Education and Training (TVET) in Nigeria: issues and suggestions for productivity and sustainable national development. *International Journal of Research in Education*, 10(1), 30-45.

Akkerman, S. F., & Bakker, A. (2011). Boundary crossing and boundary objects. *Review of Educational Research*, 81(2), 132-169.

Auta, M.; Martin Agbo, N. & Anih, I. (2023). Evaluation of Enrollment Trends into Technical Education Programmes (2013-2023) In A Nigerian University Via Documentation Analysis. *Journal of Techno Social*. 15. 37-43. 10.30880.

Bishop, J. L., & Verleger, M. A. (2013). The flipped classroom: A survey of the literature. *Journal of Educational Technology Development and Exchange*, 5(1), 1-16.

Creswell, J. W. (2014). *Research design: Qualitative, quantitative, and mixed methods approaches* (4th ed.). Sage Publications.

Dokubo, I. N. And Deebom, M, T. (2017). Gender disparity towards Students Enrollment in Technical Education in Rivers State: Causes, Effects and Strategies. *International Journal Of Research – Granthaalayah*. 5(10), 1-10. Doi: 10.5281/Zenodo.1039567

Fashoyin, T. (2014). *Industrial Relations in Nigeria (2nd edition)*, Lagos: Learn Africa.

Federal Republic of Nigeria (2013). *National Policy on Education (5th edition)*, NERDC Press.

Inyiagu, G. K. (2015). *Motivation for industrial education and technology enrolment in Nigeria*. Odessa educational books.

McInerney, D.M. (2019). Motivation. *Educational Psychology*, 39(4), 427–429
<https://doi.org/10.1080/01443410.2019.1600774>

Mohammed A. A, Ifechukwu P. A., and Nnaemeka M. A. (2023). Evaluation of Enrollment Trends into Technical Education Programmes (2013-2023) In A Nigerian University Via Documentation Analysis. *Journal of Techno-Social*. 15(2), 37-43

Njoku, N.A., Ewe, U.C. and Alio, A.N. (2017). Strategies for improving the use of ICT facilities in the teaching and learning of electronics works in technical colleges in Rivers State. *Journal of Research in Science and Technology*, 7(2), 86-96.

Njoku, N. A. (2023). Enhancing electrical/ electronics skills acquisition among technical college students for capacity building in Rivers State. *Journal of Technology*, 6(2), 26-32.

Nuru, A. (2017). *The relevance of National Vocational Education Qualification (NVQs) in TVE in Nigeria*. (Unpublished Conference Paper).

Oby, I. O. (2022). Capacity building: A veritable tool for National Development. *Journal of Humanities*, 16(1), 311-322.

Ogbondah, L. (2021). *Systemic dysfunctionalities in Nigeria's education system; which way Nigeria?* Inaugural lecture series, No 29, Ignatius Ajuru University of Education, Port Harcourt: Pearl.

Okoye, R. and Arimonu, M.O. (2016). Technical and Vocational Education in Nigeria: issue challenges and a way forward. *Journal of Education and Practice*, 7(3), 113-118.

Okwelle, P.C. and Agwi, V.I.A. (2018). Strategies for improving female students' enrolment in Technical and Vocational Education Programme through public relations activities in Nigeria. *International Journal of Advanced Academic Research/Arts, Humanities and Education* 4(1) 1-13.

Oluka, S. N. (2023). Factors Contributing to low Enrollment of Student in Technology and Vocational Education Programme in the Tertiary Institution in Enugu State.

Oviawe, J. I. (2017). Fostering Students' Enrolment in Technical Education Programmes Through Career Guidance and Occupational Awareness. *Education Journal*. 6(4), 125-132. doi: 10.11648/j.edu.20170604.11

- Puyate, S.T. and Agwi, V.I.A. (2017). Strategies for improving female students' enrolment in Technical Vocational Education and Training (TVET) programmes in Rivers and Bayelsa States. *Journal of Education in Developing Areas (JEDA)* 25(1), 65-74.
- Ukachukwu, C.C. (2015). The effect of cultural diversity on employee productivity in work organizations in Port Harcourt, Nigeria. *International Journal of Development and Management Review* 8(1), 32-49.
- Uzoeshi, K. C. & Iwundu, C. O. (2014). *Psychology of Learning*. Harey Publication.
- Uzougwu, C.B. (2014). Technical Vocational Education and Training (TVET) in Nigeria: The way forward. *Journal of Academic Excellence* 15(1), 41-49.
- Zehra, M.D. (2021). Strategies for improving students' enrolment into vocational technical education programme in North Central, Nigeria. *Vocational and Technical Education Journal* 2(2), 20-34.